

DCD Turns Milk Powder Industry Inside Out

B.K.H. Dulip Anuranga¹

Department of Commerce and Financial Management, Faculty of Commerce and
Management Studies, University of Kelaniya

Abstract: The Dicyandiamide (DCD) contamination of the milk powder in Sri Lanka caught the attention of stakeholders in the dairy industry. After the news about milk powder contaminated with DCD broke out in Sri Lanka, media and people started to protest against the so called alleged contaminated local milk powder producers and importers and both the governments of Sri Lanka and New Zealand. This case study is focused on the agitating issue popped up surrounding the milk powder industry during the period from August 2013 to December and is a descriptive analysis provided given the real scenario appeared on the newspapers, other media like internet and television. Data for the study were obtained from newspaper, journal articles and interviews had with public and doctors. The prime objective of the study is to examine the behavior of stakeholders and its implication to them and the industry.

Key words; *Dicyandiamide (DCD), Full Cream Milk Powder, Industrial Technology Institute (ITI), Multi-National Companies*

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¹ **Corresponding author's e-mail** bkhdanuranga123@gmail.com